

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT

Khalilov Bahromjon Bahodirovich

Asia International University.

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Abstract. *This article discusses the features of foreign experience in personnel management, the relationship between American and Japanese experience.*

Key words: *personnel management, personnel, personnel policy, human resource management, responsibility, selection and promotion, infrastructure, financial and intellectual capital.*

ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛОМ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются особенности зарубежного опыта управления персоналом, взаимосвязь американского и японского опыта.*

Ключевые слова: *управление персоналом, персонал, кадровая политика, управление человеческими ресурсами, ответственность, подбор и продвижение, инфраструктура, финансовый и интеллектуальный капитал.*

In the context of global competition, the reserves of mineral resources, the level of costs for wages and other production factors recede into the background in each country. The employees of an organization are of greatest importance in competition. The desire of people to achieve their goals, the knowledge and value system they possess, and their skills are the factors that ensure economic growth and well-being of the country [1].

Decisions in the field of personnel management are influenced by a number of factors that neither managers nor other employees of the company can influence. These factors are determined not only by the internal processes of the company, but also by the external environment. Often, these factors that influence personnel management methods reflect the established traditions of a particular society, and therefore are of a country-specific nature. However, there are a number of factors that depend on the technologies used at the enterprise and the products manufactured [2].

In American personnel management practice, the importance of employee initiative and responsibility, selection and promotion of personnel is especially clearly emphasized. Selection and promotion are often based on the employee's merits, as well as the employee's perceived loyalty to the organization that employs him.

In the United States, human resource management is based on an extensive research base, consultant assistance and a developed management infrastructure. Function

HR management in America is one of the most centralized. In terms of centralization, it is second only to financial centralization.

American organizations are highly competitive. Most development companies place emphasis on informal competition between employees when developing a new form of service, new products, etc. In areas where individual success is important, competition is pronounced.

In America, special attention is paid to working with personnel. Firms that use traditional personnel selection principles when hiring employees pay great attention to specialized knowledge and professional skills. Often, American specialists are professional in a narrow field of knowledge, which is why their advancement through management levels is limited, which causes

high staff turnover. Recently, the United States has been adopting the Japanese experience of combining professions.

In their personnel management policies, large American companies are guided by the following principles:

- attracting highly qualified workers from outside to form the core of the company;
- refusal of the mass use of narrow specialists with low wages in favor of qualified general workers;
- cooperation of companies with educational institutions in the development of educational programs;
- use of continuous training and advanced training;
- incentive remuneration system. The fixed part of the salary always grows. Flexible remuneration system, when part of earnings depends on overall work efficiency;
- participation of employees in the company's profits, ownership of shares;
- creation of methods to improve the quality of working life;
- participation of trade unions in the social policy of enterprises;
- formation of corporate culture.

In modern large American companies, social spending on employees is an important element of corporate culture. It is believed that social assistance from the company helps improve productivity and labor efficiency. Thus, we can talk about the impact on increasing employee loyalty to their company. From the point of view of assessing the contribution of personnel to the company's activities, productivity and economic efficiency of labor and costs per employee are assessed. In practice, as a rule, methods for assessing the effectiveness of human resource management are not systematically applied [7].

Currently, we are talking about the need to assess the contribution of personnel to the production of added value, the value of the company, etc. Initially, such ideas arose due to the difference between the market (real) and accounting value of the company. In this regard, attempts were made to value intangible assets (which include personnel) and to evaluate those indicators that are not included in the reporting. The value of market assets can actually only be determined when the company is sold; all valuations made before that are conditional. However, certain logic is used in accounting for human resources as an unaccounted asset, which also forms the value of the company.

For this assessment, the approach developed by L. Edvinsson and M. Malone is convenient. Their approach separates human and intellectual capital. Thus, it is determined the place of each of them in the value of the company. This division is based on the fact that human resources are an unstable economic resource of the company and need to accumulate competencies and experience on a more stable basis.

Thus, market value is calculated as a combination of financial and intellectual capital. The latter, in turn, includes human, customer and structural capital (organizational, innovative and technological).

Human capital is a set of personnel competencies (knowledge, skills, experience, etc.) and their conditions for implementation and updating (degree of involvement, forms of recognition, and conditions of development). At the same time, an assessment of structural capital is also

necessary, since it includes the entire necessary supporting infrastructure for the formation and use of human capital.

The formation of structural capital affects the company's image. This leads to the following task: intellectual capital must be located and maintained at a sufficiently high level, both in itself and by increasing the sustainability of human capital [7].

In Japan, the system of strategic personnel management is currently quite similar to the system in the United States. Japanese corporations manage their employees so that they work at their best. In particular, we are talking about an effective payroll system, analysis of the organization of employee labor and workplace organization, and a personnel certification system [5].

However, it is possible to note differences in the Japanese and American personnel management systems. Japanese companies place great emphasis on the dedication of employees to their organization. A strong correlation between employees and the company is of great importance, and therefore leads to high efficiency in the work process.

Since Japan is one of the most developed countries in the world, studying its experience is especially relevant. For many countries, the Japanese personnel management system has become the standard.

Of course, many Japanese corporations have different HR systems. However, there are tools that have become widespread in many Japanese enterprises over the past ten years. The advantages of these methods and the possibility of their adoption by enterprises have received wide discussion in the USA and Europe.

The main features of these methods:

- a system of lifelong employment in one company (work in one company until reaching retirement age);
- involvement of employees in planning and decision-making processes;
- organization of activities based on groups with a high degree of self-control of workers;
- open type of communication between work groups and between management and staff;
- the great importance of the seniority factor in promotions and salary increases.

The Japanese management style is characterized by respect for the individual, formed through lifelong employment, minor promotions, as well as systematic training and involvement of staff in management.

The experience of American and Japanese companies allows us to track innovations in the principles and methods of personnel management.

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